

Interdisciplinary Integration in Engineering Education: Integration of Predictive Statistical Model Generation for Chronic Disease Prediction through Fingerprint Dermatoglyphics

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Abstract

This article addresses experiences in engineering education, which focuses on integrating knowledge between the health sector and industrial engineering to develop mathematical models for predicting chronic diseases using fingerprint dermatoglyphics as a key source of information. A process has been carried out in which fingerprint dermatoglyphic has been recognized as a valuable marker for the prediction of chronic diseases, in which the combination of medical knowledge and industrial engineering skills has had an outstanding impact on the construction of a methodology for the understanding of dermatoglyphic patterns associated with the prediction of predisposition to various chronic, according to the existing literature in the health sector. Thus, the methodology established in the current study presents a detailed description of the data acquisition methods, processing techniques, and statistical analysis with which it was possible to collect and extract significant information from the dermatoglyphic impressions, it is computer processing to convert them into useful databases to conclude with a phase of statistical analysis with which it was possible to build a predictive model with a high level of accuracy and robustness in the prediction of specific chronic diseases. Finally, a descriptive analysis is made of the process of integration of knowledge from the areas of health and engineering, during the methodology being developed in the study in progress, in the aspects of construction of a common language, solution to challenges from a shared vision for the achievement of the objective and joint interpretation of results to obtain multidisciplinary conclusions about the relationship between the phenomenon under observation and the predictive model built. In summary, this article provides a vision of an experience that required the collaboration of two different but complementary disciplines to propose low-cost and non-intrusive techniques for the early detection of genetic predisposition to certain chronic diseases.

Keywords: Interdisciplinary Integration Concepts; Statistics Model Prediction; Fingerprint Dermatoglyphics; Educational Engineering Methodology.

1 Introduction

Currently, the need for interdisciplinary work has become evident to address the problems that arise in different sectors such as the economy, the use of technologies, and health and disease, to name just a few. In this sense, biotechnology has had multiple applications in different scenarios such as tissue engineering, cellular engineering, biotechnological drugs, vaccines, and identification of genetic determinants associated with various diseases (Reza, 2011).

Chronic non-communicable diseases (NCDs) affect humanity in large proportion representing a significant percentage of mortality in the population, according to the World Health Organization (WHO) 41 million people equivalent to 71% lose their lives each year due to disease (Colantonio, y otros, 2021; Seclen-Santiesteban, 2021), in the region of the Americas deaths are 5.5 million annually. The highest rate of deaths is constituted by cardiovascular pathologies representing 17.9 million people each year (PAHO/WHO, 2018). For this reason, it is essential to address strategies not only for prevention but also for early detection of these

pathologies. NCDs are divided into four major disease subgroups: cardiovascular, where hypertension and acute myocardial infarction lead morbidity rates, cancer, respiratory diseases and finally, diabetes. Together, mortality from all these diseases accounts for 75% (32 million) of the entire world population, affecting middle and low-income countries to a greater extent (Estrada-Brizuela, y otros, 2021).

The economic burden represented by the group of the four most relevant chronic noncommunicable diseases (cardiovascular, cancer, chronic respiratory, and diabetes) has a severe impact on the economic systems of each country; according to the World Health Organization, it is projected that during the period between 2011 and 2025, the cumulative loss of production of low and middle-income countries will be 7.28 trillion dollars per year (World Health Organization (WHO), 2023). A report issued by the World Economic Forum defined that this group of diseases is an important risk factor for developing high unemployment and poverty rates in a society (Pan American Health Organization (PAHO); World Health Organization (WHO), 2018).

Motivated by the current challenges, it is becoming usual the contribution from engineering to other areas of knowledge, and as mentioned one of the areas of work of biotechnology, is the digitization and digital transformation for different purposes such as the recognition of genes or genetic markers to achieve predictive models and determine risk factors for presenting a chronic noncommunicable disease (NCD) (Ibañez, Ribera, & Rodríguez-Lluesma, 2023). In this sense, dermatoglyphics, a science in charge of studying the design of papillary ridges that can present pertinent and precise data on physical and genetic characteristics that directly influence the health of the individual, can be a low-cost technique that generates information to identify risk factors and predict the appearance of pathologies that are preventable and that being diagnosed early, allow mitigating the impact on the sequels, generating well-being in the early stages of the vital cycle. It should be noted that fingerprints are formed during gestation and become a reliable indicator that remains throughout life, thus being an immutable element; papillary ridges are found on the palms of the hands which are correlated with the early manifestation of NCDs (Ghislaine-Morizon & Aspillaga, 1977). In this sense, dermatoglyphics, a science in charge of studying the design of papillary ridges that can present pertinent and precise data on physical and genetic characteristics that directly influence the health of the individual, can be a low-cost technique that generates information to identify risk factors and predict the appearance of pathologies that are preventable and that being diagnosed early, allow mitigating the impact on the sequels, generating well-being in the early stages of the vital cycle. It should be noted that fingerprints are formed during gestation and become a reliable indicator that remains throughout life, thus being an immutable element; papillary ridges are found on the palms of the hands which are correlated with the early manifestation of NCDs (Ghislaine-Morizon & Aspillaga, 1977). The use of dermatoglyphic fingerprinting as a predictive method for chronic noncommunicable diseases would provide beneficial information that would translate into a decrease in the incidence of these types of pathologies that affect human well-being, and would also alleviate the costs that they entail for the health system of each country (Girod-Frais & Bécue, 2021), Finally, it could improve primary prevention actions and thus have a positive impact on the welfare of the population in low and middle-income countries, reducing mortality rates and in general terms providing a solution to the problems experienced in recent decades at the global level (Castro-Jimenez, Rodríguez-Florian, & Rocha-Gonzalez, 2023). The use of dermatoglyphic fingerprinting as a predictive method for chronic noncommunicable diseases would provide beneficial information that would translate into a decrease in the incidence of these types of pathologies that affect human well-being, and would also alleviate the costs that they entail for the health system of each country (Girod-Frais & Bécue, 2021), Finally, it could improve primary prevention actions and thus have a positive impact on the welfare of the population in low and middle-income countries, reducing mortality rates and in general terms providing a solution to the problems experienced in recent decades at the global level (Castro-Jimenez, Rodríguez-Florian, & Rocha-Gonzalez, 2023).

Engineering contributes by proposing a model that can be applied in the field of health conditions of the population in general, which would allow early recognition of people at risk of NCDs. as has been described in different studies with methods that use neural networks as an element of categorization (Darji, Darji, Nisar, & Joshi, 2021; Alsharman, Saaidah, Almomani, Jawarneh, & Al-Qaisi, 2022), statistical methods for variations in populations (Etta, Petu, Etukudosh, & Uyannah, 2014), Deep learning for automated fingerprint identification systems (Ametefe, Sarnin, Ali, & Muhammad, 2023).

2 Methodology

2.1 Type of research

This research is framed within a quantitative approach, given that numerical data will be collected to understand cause and effect correlations that will be the object of analysis for the construction of the prediction model. The study will adopt an analytical-correlational scope and an experimental intervention strategy will be implemented. In terms of its temporal design, it is classified as cross-sectional, given that data will be collected at a single point in time with no subsequent follow-up.

2.2 Sources of information

In this research, primary sources of information are used, which were collected directly through data collection sessions in Higher Education Institutions, with students belonging to the engineering faculty of different semesters.

2.3 Data collection instruments

For the data collection of this research, different instruments were used, which are described below:

- Survey: two surveys were designed to collect data on healthy lifestyle and physical fitness assessment. The model of these surveys can be found in the appendix section (appendix 1, appendix 2).
- Elite Hem digital blood pressure monitor: It is a medical device used to measure diastolic and systolic blood pressure and pulses per minute.
- SECA portable measuring rod: An instrument used to measure a person's height.
- Tanitna Body Scale: Device used to measure a person's weight and other variables.
- Fingerprint reader WM110CA-E00: A technological device used to scan images of the ridges that make up the fingerprint.
- Statgraphics: Program used for statistical analysis of data.

2.4 Population and sample size

This section will present the results obtained from the development of the research and the generation of the mathematical model for the prediction of predisposition to suffer NCDs in students from various higher education institutions in the city of Bogota, through fingerprint dermatoglyphics.

The target population of this research is young university students, and the sample is composed of students from various institutions of higher education in the city of Bogota, who are between 18 and 26 years old, reaching a population of 400 individuals which has a sample size of 90 students.

During the data collection sessions, a sample of 90 students was obtained, the results of which indicated that, in general, the average height was 169.79 cm (SD \pm 8.12 cm), with a maximum of 189 cm and a minimum of 142.5 cm. In the weight variable, an average of 65.67 kg (SD \pm 9.79 kg) was obtained, where the maximum weight was 96.3 kg, and the minimum was 50.1 kg. In the BMI variable, the average was 22.75 Kg/Cm² (SD \pm

2.73 Kg/Cm²), where the maximum was 34.20 Kg/Cm² and the minimum was 17.45 Kg/Cm². The results of these variables by gender are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Height, weight, and BMI data for male

	Male				
	n	Mean	Deviation	Maximum	Minimum
Height	73,00	172,44	6,062296	189,00	160,50
Weight		67,64	9,418810	96,30	50,30
BMI		22,73	2,696434	34,20	17,45
%	81,11				

Table 2. Height, weight, and BMI data for female

	Female				
	n	Mean	Deviation	Maximum	Minimum
Height	17,00	158,74	5,635380	167,90	142,50
Weight		57,27	6,476180	74,10	50,10
BMI		22,80	2,965096	29,05	18,58
%	18,89				

On the other hand, in the dermatoglyphic data variables, it is evident that two figures predominate in the right hand, the first is the radial clasp with 225 figures equivalent to 50% of the total figures of the right hand, having a greater presence in finger 3 and 5 with 64 figures each. The second predominant figure is whorl 193 figures equivalent to 42.89% of the total figures of the right hand, having a greater presence in finger 1 with 58 figures.

Table 3. Dermatoglyphic data right-hand

Fingers	Dermatoglyphic data right-hand			
	Ulnar Loop	Radial Loop	Whorl	Arch
MDT1	0	32	58	0
MDT2	14	33	34	9
MDT3	1	64	20	5
MDT4	0	32	55	3
MDT5	0	64	26	0
Total	15	225	193	17
%	3,33	50,00	42,89	3,78

Concerning the left hand, the predominant figures are two, the first is the radial clasp with 233 figures equivalent to 51.77% of the total figures of the left hand, with a greater presence in finger 5 with 66 figures. The second predominant figure is the whorl with 178 figures equivalent to 39.55% of the total figures of the left hand, with a greater presence in fingers 1 and 4, both with 49 figures.

Table 4. Dermatoglyphic data left hand.

Fingers	Dermatoglyphic data left-hand			
	Ulnar Loop	Radial Loop	Whorl	Arch
MET1	0	35	49	6
MET2	15	31	36	8
MET3	2	61	21	6
MET4	0	40	49	1
MET5	0	66	23	1
Total	17	233	178	22
%	3,78	51,78	39,56	4,89

Variables selection

Twenty-two variables were selected from the sample of 30 students that met the description of the target population. After having the data in tables, the relevant variables were selected for the construction of the mathematical model, which is described below.

Independent variables

MDSQL1: Right-hand finger 1 crest.
 MDSQL2: Right-hand finger 2 crests
 MDSQL3: Right-hand finger 3 crests
 MDSQL4: Right-hand finger 4 crests
 MDSQL5: Right-hand finger 5 crests
 MESQL1: Left-hand finger 1 crest
 MESQL2: Left-hand finger 2 crests
 MESQL3: Left-hand finger 3 crests
 MESQL4: Left-hand finger 4 crests
 MESQL5: Left-hand finger 5 crests

MDT1: Figure type finger 1 right hand
 MDT2: Figure type finger 2 right hand
 MDT3: Figure type finger 3 right hand
 MDT4: Figure type finger 4 right hand
 MDT5: Figure type finger 5 right hand
 MET1: Type of figure finger 1 left hand
 MET2: Type of figure finger 2 left hand
 MET3: Type of figure finger 3 left hand
 MET4: Type of figure finger 4 left hand
 MET5: Type of figure finger 5 left hand

Dependent variables

Depending on the type of chronic non-communicable disease on which the analysis is focused, several dependent variables can be taken, such as:

DBP: Diastolic Blood Pressure of the Individual at Rest.
 SBP: Systolic Blood Pressure of the Individual at Rest
 RRF: Resting Respiration Rate
 BMI: Body Mass Index
 % FAT: Percentage of body fat

2.5 Participation of industrial engineering students in the development of the research project.

The participating industrial engineering students were linked to the research project through the formative research course, which in the development of their undergraduate studies corresponds to a level of training in basic research skills for the formulation of a degree project with which they can opt for the title of industrial engineer, this course corresponds to a ninth of ten semesters required to fulfill the academic program.

Thus, a requirement for the linking of students in the research project in the area of dermatoglyphics was to possess technological skills in the use of measurement tools, socialization skills to interact with other members, and cognitive skills in the collection, analysis and synthesis of statistical data from samples, aspects required according to the literature in the formation of engineering skills at the technological, socialization and emotional level for the year 2030 in the West; (Dahl, Tvenge, Assuad, & Martinsen, 2023; Ellingrud, Gupta, & Salguero, 2020)

Thus, the students participating in the research project with training in industrial engineering required a professional profile different from the traditional training in this nucleus of knowledge in Colombia. This aspect required the development of complementary competencies through multidisciplinary training sessions and practical actions framed within the scope of the project as referred to in the following sections of this document.

Once the students who met these requirements were selected, a team of nine people was formed, composed of one teacher from the health area, two teachers from the engineering area, five undergraduate students in industrial engineering, and five students from programs in the area of health as a professional in physical culture, professional sport, and recreation, These students started a first training from the health area to carry out the measurement process with the instruments available to measure the variables of height, weight, heart rate, respiratory frequency and blood pressure in each individual in an adequate manner.

Subsequently, the work team performed the measurements on the ninety individuals participating in the study after signing informed consent for the use of the information, which was explained by each member of the team in an empathetic manner and simple terms, an aspect that required social and emotional competence, this measurement was performed in a series of sessions in which each individual was measured in height and weight by an engineering student, while the measurement of the respiratory frequency and blood pressure was performed by a student in the area of health.

Additionally, once this process of measurement of physical characteristics had been carried out, each individual had each of the ten fingerprints of each of the fingers of their hands taken through a digital scanner, which was done by the teacher of the health area and the students of both study areas, to guarantee the legibility of the fingerprints and their correct digital storage in a digital file for each individual.

The previous process of capturing fingerprints required a second training process in scanner image reading skills, in which all teachers and students of both areas participated, for which it was necessary to formulate specifications for the development of this activity properly, to achieve a correct reading of the fingerprint and the storage of the information necessary for the study.

Then, based on these measurements, it was necessary to carry out a third training session from the health area, in which concepts such as the estimation of the body mass index were addressed, as well as the identification of the figures present in the fingerprints, such as radial and ulnar loops, arches and whorls, their forms of recognition and interpretation in digital files to consolidate the database of independent variables already stated earlier in this article.

Table 5. Competencies, skills, and tools desired in industrial engineering students for their participation in the research project.

Competences	Skills	Tools
Technological Competencies	Measurement and data collection	Use scales, blood pressure monitors, measuring devices, fingerprint readers, etc.
	Use of Software	Watson Fingerprint Recognition Software
Socials Competencies	Communication Skills	Communicate clearly and effectively with participants, explaining the purpose of data collection, instructions for making measurements, and answering any questions or concerns from participants.
	Empathy and Cultural Sensitivity Ability	To interact with people from diverse cultures, backgrounds, and socioeconomic levels, demonstrating empathy and respect for individual differences. This is important to create an environment of trust and comfort during data collection.
	Ethics and privacy	Understand and adhere to ethical principles and privacy standards related to the collection and handling of biometric data. They must ensure the confidentiality of the information collected and obtain informed consent from participants before any measurements are taken.
	Ability to manage difficult situations	Prior preparation to deal with difficult or unexpected situations during data collection, such as identifying potential health problems or managing participants who may feel uncomfortable or anxious during the process.
Cognitive Competencies	Collaboration and teamwork	It is important that they can work collaboratively with other health professionals, researchers, or university staff involved in the data collection project, ensuring effective coordination and integrity of the data collected.
	Statistical Analysis	Strong understanding of statistical principles, including probability distributions, descriptive statistics, statistical inference, and multivariate techniques. This will enable them to perform exploratory data analysis and assess the significance of relationships between variables.
	Mathematical Modelling	Knowledge of mathematical modeling techniques, including linear and nonlinear regression, time series analysis, logistic regression models, and survival analysis, among others. This will allow them to develop predictive and explanatory models based on the data collected.
	Accurate recording and documentation skills	Rigorous recording and documentation of the data collected, ensuring that the information is complete, accurate, and organized for further analysis and use.

Once the measurements of the physical characteristics, as well as the type of figures and number of characteristics of each of the ten fingerprints of the participants, each of the team members participated in the development of a database containing the necessary information to make a projection model of own conditions in the description of chronic noncommunicable disease, so that independent variables are derived from the measurement of weight, height, number of figures and type of figures as independent variables, as well as body mass index, diastolic and systolic blood pressure as dependent variables.

Once the database is consolidated, a fourth training session is carried out from the engineering area in which the topic of statistical projection models is dealt with through general linear models in which the criteria for information analysis are established such as reduction of coefficients, variance analysis and formulation of the general linear model, which is part of the set of knowledge proper to the study of industrial engineering. This aspect is consolidated in the objective of the project for its use and dissemination in the academic community interested in these topics. (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Main Phases and Activities of participation in the research project by area of knowledge.

3 Results

The research project was carried out with the participation of students of engineering and health, achieved at the end of the stage of analysis and synthesis of information collected from the participating individuals the following general linear model with which it is possible to predict the body mass index of each individual from the information of the number and type of figures present in the fingerprints:

3.1 Coefficient reduction

In this aspect of coefficient reduction through the analysis of four statistical measures of adjusted R-squared, unadjusted R-squared, Mallows Cp, and mean square of the error (MSE), it was possible to establish that the number of coefficients suitable for use in the statistical model to determine the body mass index used eighteen coefficients with an 84.8% explanation rate from the predictor variables.

3.2 Analysis of variance of the general linear model

After obtaining the sensitive variables of the multiple regression model, a regression analysis of the linear model is performed with these variables, obtaining a mathematical model that represents the data set. According to the calculation of the P-value in the analysis of variance table for BMI is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant relationship between BMI and the predictor variables with a confidence level of 95.0%.

Table 5. Analysis of variance for BMI

Source	Sum of Squares	Gl	Medium Square	F-Ratio	P-Value
Model	234,511	18	13,0284	3,42	0,0211
Residue	41,9441	11	3,8131		
Total (Corr.)	276,455	29			

3.3 General linear model for BMI prediction

The general linear model that explains a level of 84.8% of the body mass index from the fingerprint study is as follows:

$$\text{IMC} = 31,8544 + 1,42142 \cdot I1(1) + 1,956 \cdot I2(1) + 0,549131 \cdot I2(2) - 0,482455 \cdot I2(3) - 4,29804 \cdot I3(1) + 1,3485 \cdot I3(2) + 3,0337 \cdot I4(1) + 2,48367 \cdot I4(2) + 0,2508 \cdot I5(1) + 3,24892 \cdot I5(2) + 1,04156 \cdot I5(3) - 1,93294 \cdot I6(1) + 0,3515 \cdot \text{MDSQL1} - 0,0431056 \cdot \text{MDSQL2} - 0,601223 \cdot \text{MDSQL4} + 0,671739 \cdot \text{MDSQL5} - 0,496272 \cdot \text{MESQL1} - 0,51592 \cdot \text{MESQL2}$$

Where:

$I1(1) = 1$ if MDT1=2, -1 if MDT1=3, 0 in other case	$I4(1) = 1$ if MET1=2, -1 if MET1=4, 0 in other case
$I2(1) = 1$ if MDT2=1, -1 if MDT2=4, 0 in other case	$I4(2) = 1$ if MET1=3, -1 if MET1=4, 0 in other case
$I2(2) = 1$ if MDT2=2, -1 if MDT2=4, 0 in other case	$I5(1) = 1$ if MET2=1, -1 if MET2=4, 0 in other case
$I2(3) = 1$ if MDT2=3, -1 if MDT2=4, 0 in other case	$I5(2) = 1$ if MET2=2, -1 if MET2=4, 0 in other case
$I3(1) = 1$ if MDT3=2, -1 if MDT3=4, 0 in other case	$I5(3) = 1$ if MET2=3, -1 if MET2=4, 0 in other case
$I3(2) = 1$ if MDT3=3, -1 if MDT3=4, 0 in other case	$I6(1) = 1$ if MET4=2, -1 if MET4=3, 0 in other case

4 Conclusions

According to the development of this project and the statistical analysis of the results, where the general objective is to design a mathematical model for predicting the predisposition to non-communicable chronic diseases developed from data collected from a population of 400 students from higher education institutions in the city of Bogotá, with a sample of 90 individuals randomly selected, it is concluded that:

Engaging industrial engineering students in interdisciplinary field research holds paramount significance in their academic and professional development. Collaborative endeavors with experts across diverse domains, notably the healthcare sector, facilitate the cultivation of invaluable skills imperative for their future roles. Through such collaborative initiatives, students are not only equipped with effective interdisciplinary communication abilities but also adept at navigating disparate methodologies inherent in varied disciplines. This multifaceted exposure fosters a comprehensive comprehension of intricate challenges, thereby nurturing critical thinking, creativity, and innovative problem-solving approaches. Moreover, practical engagement in field research offers students tangible experiences, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world applications. Consequently, these immersive learning experiences empower industrial engineering students to emerge as versatile professionals capable of addressing multifarious challenges within healthcare and beyond, catalyzing positive transformations through their innovative solutions.

During the evaluation and collection of dermatoglyphic data, a critical activity has been identified that prolongs the duration of the information collection sessions. This activity consists of individually taking fingerprints for each finger, which causes a delay in the session.

The process of selecting the most relevant and significant dermatoglyphic variables for predicting obesity has been fundamental to the development of this project. During this process, various dermatoglyphic variables were identified and analyzed for subsequent modeling in the statistical program Statgraphics. At the end of this process, twenty independent variables were selected, which refer to the number of ridges in the fingerprints and the types of existing patterns, and two dependent variables, which are BMI (Body Mass Index) and FAT% (Body Fat Percentage).

During the modeling of the selected variables using the Statgraphics program, the effectiveness of this tool as an optimal resource for statistical analysis was evident. Stat graphics proved to be a comprehensive tool that

provides a wide variety of graphs and tables, significantly contributing to the analysis of the model performed. The graphs generated by the program allowed for a clear and concise visualization of the relationship between the variables, facilitating the interpretation of the results and the identification of relevant patterns or trends.

In the BMI variable model, it is evident that out of the twelve analyzed sensitive variables, two are significant for predicting obesity: MDSQL1 (right thumb) and MDSQL2 (Right Hand Index finger). Additionally, when analyzing the %FAT model, it is observed that the sensitive variables that this model yields are present in the variables of the BMI model. Out of the seven sensitive variables yielded by the %FAT model, two are significant for predicting the percentage of body fat, which are MDSQL4 (Right-Hand ring finger) and MDSQL5 (Right-Hand little finger). Therefore, it is concluded that these two variables are also related to predicting obesity in students from higher education institutions in Bogotá.

Industrial engineering students can play a crucial role in interdisciplinary integration with the healthcare sector through various strategies:

Process Analysis: Industrial engineers are trained to analyse and improve processes in different contexts. In the healthcare sector, this involves identifying areas of inefficiency in medical care, from patient admission to discharge, and proposing solutions to optimize workflows and reduce waiting times.

Supply Chain Optimization: Industrial engineering students can apply their knowledge of supply chain management to improve the distribution of medical supplies and medications, ensuring their availability at the right times and places. This is essential for ensuring effective and timely medical care.

Quality Management System Design: Quality principles and continuous improvement are fundamental in both industry and the healthcare sector. Industrial engineering students can help implement quality management systems in hospitals and clinics, ensuring that standards are met, and medical errors are minimized.

Application of Technology and Data Analysis: Technological advancements are transforming healthcare, and industrial engineers can contribute to their implementation and optimization. For example, they can develop information systems and data analysis tools to improve patient monitoring, medical record management, and clinical decision-making.

Design of Facilities and Medical Equipment: Knowledge of facility and equipment design are key skills of industrial engineers that can be applied in the healthcare sector. From designing hospitals and clinics to optimizing the design of medical devices, industrial engineering students can contribute to creating safer and more efficient healthcare environments.

Interdisciplinary collaboration with the healthcare sector is crucial for training industrial engineers. By integrating knowledge from both fields, industrial engineers can contribute innovative solutions to enhance healthcare systems' efficiency, safety, and accessibility. They can develop technologies and processes that optimize resource management, streamline workflows, and improve patient care outcomes through collaboration. This synergy between engineering and healthcare fosters innovation and addresses complex challenges facing the healthcare industry, ultimately benefiting society.

5 Recommendations

Considering the importance of this research work and based on the results obtained, recommendations are made for both teachers and students who wish to continue this line of research. In the fingerprinting activity, it is recommended to work with equipment that allows for the collection of fingerprints from more than one finger at a time, as this will streamline the process, reducing the time required for data collection sessions.

For researchers and teachers, it is recommended to implement a program containing a Machine Learning code, which will enable them to analyse fingerprints in an agile and rapid manner, as this process is the most time-consuming when done manually. It is important to be rigorous in ensuring that all requested data are obtained to avoid the culling of many individuals, which could result in a lack of a robust and consolidated database for research purposes. Students who wish to continue with this line of research are advised to review studies related to dermatoglyphics and statistics to better understand and analyse the results obtained from the statistical program.

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